

A CASE STUDY ON WILSON'S DISEASE

Sriram Shanmugam^{*,1}, Jaeann Ann Kennady^{*} and Jaleel Ahamed^{**}

^{*}Department of Pharmacy Practice, College of Pharmacy, SRIPMS, Coimbatore., ^{**}Consultant Paediatrician, Sri Ramakrishna Hospital, Coimbatore.

ABSTRACT Background: Wilson's disease is a rare autosomal recessive disorder characterised by the accumulation of copper in the liver, brain, cornea and kidneys. This is a hospital-based study; there are no community-based prevalence and incidence studies of Wilson's disease in India. **Case Summary:** An eleven-year-old female girl was presented to the paediatric department with significant complaints of yellowish discolouration of eyes, high coloured urine, fever, swelling of feet and abdominal distention. Using the elevated levels of ceruloplasmin, urine copper and the presence of KF rings on both eyes Wilson's disease with decompensated cirrhosis was confirmed. She was treated with copper chelators (D- penicillamine & Zinc) and antioxidants. Gradually she showed improvement in clinical signs and LFT. **Conclusion:** Wilson's disease is an inherited metabolic disorder. Early diagnosis and appropriate management help to prevent the systemic complications. Siblings needed to be screened to prevent manifestations. It also points out the need to suspect Wilson's disease in any young patient presented with the unexplained liver disease.

KEYWORDS Wilson's disease, Copper accumulation, KF rings

Introduction

Wilson's disease is a rare autosomal recessive disorder of copper metabolism caused by mutation of ATP7B gene on chromosome 13 resulting in a systemic overload of copper. It is also known as hepatolenticular degeneration (hepato- liver, lenticular- brain), where the copper is deposited in brain, liver, kidney, eyes etc. The ATP7B gene encodes P-type adenosine triphosphate family of copper transporter protein (ceruloplasmin); due to the mutation in this gene in Wilson's disease synthesis of ceruloplasmin is impaired. Copper is an essential content of many metabolic enzymes. Normal estimated total body copper is 50-100mg, and average daily intake is 2-5mg. The amount of copper in the body is normal at birth. Afterwards, it increases steadily. The symptoms usually begin between the age of 5 and 45 years. Hepatic manifestations presented with acute hepatitis which may progress to fulminant liver failure characterised by ascites, spi-

der nevi, palmar erythema and digital clubbing. Neurological damage causes tremor, choreoathetosis, dystonia and dementia. Kayser Fleisher ring is the salient feature and can be seen less often in children. It is characterised by a greenish-brown discolouration of corneal margin which gradually disappears with treatment.

COPPER METABOLISM AND DEPOSITION

After absorption copper is transported to hepatocytes where it is incorporated with enzymes and copper-binding proteins (Ceruloplasmin). Excess copper forms complex with apometallothionine and the copper-metallothionine complex is excreted via bile.

In Wilson's disease incorporation of copper to ceruloplasmin and excretion of excess copper into bile are impaired. Excess copper generates free radicals resulting in oxidation of lipids and proteins. It also accumulates in liver and damages the hepatocytes. Once the liver copper level increases, it started to get a deposit in other organs. The deliverance of free copper into the blood causes hemolysis and renal tubulopathy.

Low serum ceruloplasmin is a pointer to the diagnosis. Other parameters include high free serum copper, high urine copper excretion and D- penicillamine challenge test [1]. Wilson's disease is a genetic disorder that found worldwide. The prevalence of Wilson's disease is 1 per 30,000 individuals, and the incidence is 10-30 million cases. There is no community-based prevalence in India, but it is more common where consanguinity is prevalent (south India) [2].

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¹sriram shanmugam, Department of Pharmacy Practice, College of Pharmacy, SRIPMS, Coimbatore E-mail: visitram@yahoo.com

This case is a unique presentation of Wilson's disease with clear KF rings and without neurological involvement. Timely diagnosis and appropriate management helped to reduce the morbidity and mortality. Hence it points out the need to suspect Wilson's disease in any young patient presented with the unexplained liver disease.

Table 1 prognostic index in fulminant Wilsonian hepatitis[2]

	0	1	2	3	4
Sr. Bilirubin(3-20µmol/L)	<100	100-150	151-300	201-300	>300
Sr. AST(7-40IU/L)	<100	100-150	151-300	301-400	>400
PT(sec.)	<4	4-8	9-12	13-20	>20
≥ 11 indicates poor prognosis and mortality in liver disorder					

CASE PRESENTATION

An eleven-year-old female girl from south India was presented to the paediatric department with major complaints of yellowish discoloration of eyes, high coloured urine, fever, swelling of feet and abdominal distention. She was normal 15 days back and developed a sudden onset of fever and taken to the private practitioner and jaundice was noted. She was given with native treatment (Nattuvaidyam) for a day and sent home. She developed abdominal distention and swelling of feet past two days. She was an IVF baby immunised for age and had menarche two months back and no menstrual cycle after.

Patient weighed 32kg had an elevated body temperature of 100.7°F. On examination, she was conscious with Icterus, Clubbing, and B/L pedal oedema and ascites. Her USG showed hepatosplenomegaly(hepatomegaly 6cm↓ RCM, splenomegaly 8cm↓ LCM). One episode of epistaxis was observed on the day of admission.

LAB INVESTIGATIONS

Parameters	D1	D2	D3	D4
Total Bilirubin (mg/dl)	8.2	18.5	11	10.9
Bilirubin direct(mg/dl)	6.2	14.7	9.1	8.8
Bilirubin indirect(mg/dl)	2	3.8	1.9	2.10
Total protein(g/dl)	7.5	7.2	6.8	7
Albumin(g/dl)	2.6	2.4	2.5	2.6
Globulin(g/dl)	4.9	4.8	4.4	5.4
ALP(U/L)	111	60	62	79
ALT(U/L)	228	119	71	78
AST(U/L)	1328	799	266	278
PT(sec.)	24	27	24	23
INR	1.7	2.1	1.7	1.7

The initial diagnosis was made as viral hepatitis and started with hepatoprotectants, N-Acetylcysteine and antioxidants. Elevated CRP (4.7mg/dl) and Procalcitonin(1.6ng/ml) indicated the presence of infection and started with IV antibiotics paracetamol was ordered for elevated body temperature. Control of oedema was achieved with spironolactone. On the third day of admission, her Sr. Ceruloplasmin level was found to be lower (19.9). On sixth-day urine, copper results came with an elevated value of 1394.46(<60µg/24hr) and the Coombs test, ANA, and AMA found to be positive. On suspected of Wilson's disease a slit lamp examination of eyes was performed and revealed the presence of Kayser Fleischer rings on both eyes.

Figure 1:KF ring.

Using these parameters patient was diagnosed with Wilson's

disease with decompensated cirrhosis (AMA+ related to native drugs). She was restricted to low copper containing diet and advised to avoid chocolates, liver, mushrooms and nuts strictly. Her anti-oxidant drug with copper content was stopped and narrowed the therapy with hepatoprotectants, D penicillamine zinc and vitamin K.

She was reviewed by a gastroenterologist who pointed out the need for liver transplantation. They have instructed to perform the screening for her younger sibling to rule out Wilson's disease.

Figure 2: key dates in diagnosis

DISCUSSION

Wilson's disease is a rare autosomal recessive disorder characterised by the accumulation of copper in the liver, brain, cornea and kidneys. It may be present at any age, the majority between 5 and 35 years. It is a progressive disease and could be fatal if left untreated, but the timely diagnosis remains a challenge [4].

Our patient had yellowish discolouration of eyes, high coloured urine, swelling of feet, abdominal distention and elevated LFTs which indicates the liver disease, the initial feature of Wilson's disease. Neurological features of the disease were absent in our patient. It occurs when the excess copper accumulated in the lenticular region of the brain and presented with difficulty in walking, anxiety, mood swings and depression [4,5]. Kayser Fleisher rings were identified in the patient within three weeks of hepatic presentation.

Treatment of Wilson's disease includes copper chelators like Penicillamine and Zinc. Hepatoprotectants were used as a supportive measure, where the liver transplantation is the lifesaving measure of advanced Wilson's disease [4].

CONCLUSION

Wilson's disease is an inherited metabolic disorder. It should be suspected in young patients presented with unexplained hepatic complications. Early diagnosis and appropriate management help to prevent the systemic complications. Adherence to therapy, low copper diet and proper follow-up shows a significant reduction in morbidity and mortality. Liver transplantation is recommended in acute liver failure. Siblings needed to be screened to prevent manifestations.

AUTHORS' STATEMENTS

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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